

Spinal Dysraphism – A Descriptive Retrospective Study**Hemavathi Ayyappan¹, Puneet Shirbur², Valambige Mudalagirigowda Puttaraju³**¹Radiology Resident, Department of Radiodiagnosis, MVJ Medical College and Research Hospital, Kolathur, Hoskote Taluk, affiliated Rajiv Gandhi University of Health Sciences, Bengaluru²Associate Professor, Department of Radiodiagnosis, MVJ Medical College and Research Hospital, Kolathur, Hoskote Taluk, affiliated Rajiv Gandhi University of Health Sciences, Bengaluru³Professor, Department of Radiodiagnosis, MVJ Medical College and Research Hospital, Kolathur, Hoskote Taluk, affiliated Rajiv Gandhi University of Health Sciences, Bengaluru

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Abstract:

Spinal dysraphism (SD) is a diverse group of congenital spinal anomalies resulting from incomplete closure of the neural tube during embryonic development. This retrospective study aimed to assess the role of MRI in identifying various forms of SD, characterizing the lesions, and detecting associated anomalies in a rural population. A total of 25 patients with SD were included. The most common SDs were spina bifida with tethered cord, followed by meningocele, vertebral segmentation anomalies, diastematomyelia, myelomeningocele, and dorsal dermal sinus. Associated anomalies, including syrinx, dural ectasia, scoliosis, and Chiari I malformation, were frequently observed. MRI proved to be a valuable tool in the comprehensive evaluation of SD. It allowed for accurate diagnosis, characterization of lesions, identification of associated anomalies, and planning of appropriate management strategies. Early diagnosis and timely intervention are crucial for optimizing outcomes in patients with SD.

Keywords: Spinal dysraphism, congenital spinal anomalies, spina bifida, myelomeningocele, diastematomyelia, syrinx, dural ectasia, caudal regression syndrome.

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Introduction

Congenital malformations of the spine and spinal cord are generally described under the umbrella term spinal dysraphisms (SDs) [1]. These spinal anomalies are broadly classified as open and closed types. Open spinal dysraphism is associated with a defect in the overlying skin through which neural tissue is exposed to the environment. In closed form, the neural tissue is covered by intact skin. Both forms are associated with varying degrees of neural tissue involvement [2].

Spinal dysraphism has an estimated incidence of 1-3/1000 live births. The incidence has decreased significantly in the last few decades due to folic acid supplementation in pregnant females, antenatal screening with high resolution ultrasound, and availability of biochemical markers [3,4]. Although most live cases are diagnosed at birth or early in the life, some occult forms may not be detected until adulthood [5]. Availability of MRI has facilitated early identification of occult variety, visualization of other associated anomalies in both open and closed forms, understanding of their clinical consequences, and provision of individually tailored management plans [6,7]. The purpose of this article is to review

the MRI features of spinal dysraphism presented to our hospital in rural population.

Aim of the Study:

To assess the role of MRI in the identification of various forms of spinal dysraphism, characterization of the lesions and associated anomalies, giving a composite diagnosis based on specific Imaging findings.

Material and Methods:

A retrospective study was done and cases found to have spinal dysraphism on MRI spine done at MVJ Medical College and Research Hospital, Hoskote, Bangalore from December 2021 to July 2024 were included.

Inclusion Criteria:

All patients with dimple, tuft of hair, nevi, lumbosacral swelling, open spinal dysraphic states and neurological problems were included in the study.

Data was evaluated retrospectively for all patients. Age, gender, indication for MRI, operative status, and neuroradiological features (including site and type of lesion) were recorded. Based on the presence or absence of intact overlying skin, patients were

divided into two categories: open spinal dysraphism, and closed spinal dysraphism. Data was entered and analyzed using SPSS v20.0. Descriptive statistics were used to describe the basic features of the data and associated anomalies.

Results:

25 patients found to have spinal dysraphism on MRI spine done at MVJ Medical College and Research Hospital, Hoskote, Bangalore from December 2021 to July 2024 were included in our study. Age of the

patients ranged from 0 days to 68 yr. One patient had a surgery performed on them previously. Congenital spinal malformations were more frequent in children and young adults between 0–23 years of age (Table 1). Most of the children are below 4 years of age. Of the 25 patients, 11 were female patients and 14 were male patients (Table 2). Of the 25 patients, 6 were open type and 19 were closed type of spinal dysraphism (Table 3).

Table 1: Age distribution of cases

Age group	No of cases	Percentage
Infants	5	20
Child	9	36
Adults	11	44

Table 2: Gender distribution of cases

Gender	No of cases	Percentage
Male	14	56
Female	11	44

Table 3: Type of Spinal Dysraphism

Type	No of cases	Percentage
Open	6	24
Closed	19	76

Table 4: Summary of cases

Imaging Findings	No of Cases	Percentage
Myelomeningocele	3	12
Meningocele	6	24
Filum terminale lipoma	1	4
Caudal regression syndrome	1	4
Dorsal dermal sinus	3	12
Diastematomyelia	5	20
Segmental spinal dysgenesis	6	24

Dysraphic spinal anomalies without subcutaneous masses were more common than congenital lesions with subcutaneous masses. Over all, Spina bifida with tethered cord were the most common

congenital spinal lesion observed in 12 (48%) patients, followed by meningocele, vertebral segmentation anomalies, diastematomyelia, myelomeningocele and dorsal dermal sinus.

Table 5: Location of Spinal Dysraphism

Location	No of Cases	Percentage
Cervical	3	15
Dorsal	0	0
Dorso-Lumbar	2	8
Lumbar	9	36
Sacral	3	15
Lumbosacral	8	32

The commonest vertebral anomaly was spina bifida (53.5%). Common associated spinal lesions with all these dysraphic anomalies were tethered cord and scoliosis.

Syrinx was the most common associated spinal abnormality 6 (21%) of the cases with congenital

malformations followed by dural ectasia in 5 (20%) patients. Other frequently observed associated abnormalities included scoliosis and Chiari I malformation in 4 (16%) patients each.

Among the patients with diastematomyelia, Type II was more common than Type I. Split cord

malformations were more common in lumbar spine (36%) followed by lumbosacral (32%).

Table 6: Associated Findings with Spinal Dysraphism

Associations	No of Cases	Percentage
Spina bifida	12	48
Chiari I	4	16
Hydrocephalus	2	8
Syringohydromyelia	6	24
Tethered Cord / Low lying cord	11	44
Scoliosis	4	16
Dural Ectasia	5	20
Skin manifestations	3	12
AnoRectal Malformations	1	4
Urinary Malformations	1	4
Basilar invagination/ CVJ anomaly	1	4
Cerebellar / vermian hypoplasia	1	4
Dermoid cyst	1	4
Bone Tumour	1	4

Case 1:

A late preterm female baby aged one day, born out of twin gestation to the mother with gestational diabetes mellitus presented with large lumbosacral mass at birth. On physical examination of the lumbosacral mass: mass was located in lumbo-sacral region, measuring approximately 10 x 12 cm in size, it was trans-illuminant. Skin over the lesion was stretched out, erythematous and showed multiple dilated veins. Baby's tone was normal, moving all four limbs with no significant neurological deficits. The MRI of whole spine screening and lumbosacral spine revealed spina bifida at S1 and S2 vertebrae with absence of paraspinal muscles at this level. A skin defect measuring approximately 11 mm in size in the superior-inferior plane with herniation of

cauda equina nerve roots into large thin walled enlarged cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) filled structure measuring approximately 51 x 73 x 71 mm in size. The diagnosis of open spinal dysraphism with myelomeningocele was made. The MRI of Brain in the same neonate revealed small posterior fossa with herniation of cerebellar tonsil ~ 6mm below the McRae's line. There is also herniation of distal part of pons and medulla below this line. There was dilatation of bilateral lateral ventricles (left > right), Evan's index is 0.26 – suggestive of early ventriculomegaly.

The final diagnosis of Arnold Chiari malformation with associated open spinal dysraphism and myelomeningocele was made (Figure 1). The patient was referred to

Figure 1: Appearance of lumbosacral mass b), c) T2 sag and axial images showing large CSF filled sac (yellow + sign) with hypointense nerve roots within (dashed yellow arrow). d) T2 axial showing dilatation of bilateral lateral ventricles e) T2 sag showing cerebellar tonsil and medulla herniation through foramen magnum. f) showing large sac (*) with nerve roots (→).

Plain radiographs of the lumbosacral spine revealed non-visualization of the sacrum (beyond S3) and coccyx. MRI study of whole spine revealed: Abnormal thickening and abrupt termination of the conus medullaris (Cigar shaped conus) above the expected level at the lower end of the D12 vertebra with associated tethering of the spinal cord. Syrinx in the spinal cord from T3 to T8 vertebral level. Abnormal widening of the spinal canal from T10

vertebral level onwards. The separation of anterior and posterior spinal roots of cauda equina showing ‘double-bundle appearance is noted. Agenesis of S5 and coccyx vertebra. Severe narrowing of spinal canal rostral to last intact S4 vertebra. Partial block vertebra involving S2, S3 and S4 vertebral bodies. Hypoplastic iliac bones. Lumbarisation of S1 vertebra. Neurosurgeon for further management. Follow up of this patient could not be done.

Figure 2: a) T2 Sag: abruptly terminating, abnormally thickened and tethered cigar shaped conus (*) with agenesis of S5 and Coccyx. b) T1 sag: ‘double-bundle appearance of cauda equine roots (Red →). c) T2 Sag: T2 hyperintense syrinx from D3 to D8.

Case 2:

A 2 year old male child -known case of caudal regression syndrome (Figure 2) with history of surgery for imperforate anus came for follow up MRI to our department. On physical examination there was small pelvis, small flat buttocks and a short intergluteal cleft. Colostomy site was noted in the anterior abdominal wall and it was healthy.

Narrowing of pelvis with significant atrophy of bilateral gluteal muscles.

Case 3:

A 32 year old male patient presented with complains of low back ache on and off since few years. On physical examination, local area of hypertrichosis with sacral dimple was noted in the lower back at midline.

MRI study of lumbosacral region revealed: Mild reduction in lumbar lordosis. Splitting of the lumbar spinal cord at the level of mid body of L4 vertebra in to two hemi-cords, which are enclosed within a single common dural sac. At the level of mid body of L5 vertebra, there is a thin, obliquely oriented

osseous septum dividing the lower lumbar spinal canal into two separate dural sacs, each containing a hemicord. Immediately inferior to this osseous septum, the terminal cone of the lumbar spinal cord is seen to reunite into a single cone. Low lying conus medullaris which is terminating at the level of inferior end plate of L5 vertebra. Mild progressive widening of the lumbar spinal canal caudally, in the sagittal plane – suggestive of mild /subtle dural ectasia. A thin, linear, horizontally oriented hypointense band on T1W, T2W and SPACE sequence, coursing across the subcutaneous tissue plane of the lower back at the level of superior aspect of the L5 vertebral body, terminating as a thick area onto the skin – suggestive of fibrous dorsal sinus tract. NCCT scan study of the lumbar spine reveals: Bifid spine of the L4, L5 and sacrum – consistent with lower lumbar and sacral spina bifida occulta.

The above imaging features are consistent with closed complex spinal dysraphism with combination of Type I and Type II split cord malformation/diastematomyelia and dorsal dermal sinus tract (Figure 3).

Figure 3: a) Hypertrichosis with skin dimple. b) CT Axial and c) Plain Xray LS apine AP: non-fusion of spinal process of L4 and L5 - Spinal bifida, d) Spina bifida of sacral elements. e) CT Sag, f) CT Axial– fibrous septum in spinal canal at L5 vertebra level (red arrow). g) T1 Sag- low lying conus (+), T2 hypointense tract -dorsal dermal sinus (*). i) T2 Sag – splitting of cord (+) with septum at L5 level (Red→), j) STIR Cor and k) T2 axial –Showing two hemicords with separate dural sac (yellow→).

Case 4: A 25 year old male patient came with complains of pain in the lower back. A tuft of hair is seen at the midline of the lower back just above the superior margin of the gluteal cleft.

Figure 4:

The low lying conus medullaris, terminates at the level of upper body of L4 vertebra. The Filum terminale is also mildly prominent. Short segment syrinx in the dorsal aspect of the distal spinal cord and proximal conus medullaris measuring about 1.6 cm in length and located opposite the inferior half of body of L2 vertebra.

Focal mild widening of the spinal canal at the lower sacral level containing a CSF filled sac – consistent with low sacral meningocele. Complementary CT scan study of the lumbosacral spine reveals sacral spina bifida at the level of third sacral segment. Mild widening of the spinal canal and thecal sac in the

lower lumbar and upper sacral region suggestive of lower lumbar dural ectasia. The imaging features are consistent with closed spinal dysraphism with low sacral meningocele.

Axial and angled coronal sections through the sacral spine reveals a focal, oval shaped, multiloculated lesion in the posteromedial aspect of the left iliac bone measuring about 4.7 x 1.9 x 2 cm in size. This lesion reveals hyperintense signal intensity on T2W and STIR sequences with multiple residual bony trabeculae traversing the lesion. No obvious fluid levels are noted within this lesion – suggestive of Giant Cell Tumor. (Figure 4)

Figure 5: a) T1 Sag – low lying conus medullaris with prominent filum terminale (yellow →). b) T2 hyperintense syrinx within cord and dural ectasia (green <->). c) T2 and STIR Cor– well defined hyperintense

lesion in the sacral region (* - Meningocele) and multiloculated hyperintense lesion with multiple trabeculae in left iliac bone (red → GCT). e) T2 axial – Non fusion of spinous process of S3 – spina bifida.

Case 5:

A 27 year old female patient came with complains of back pain and left lower limb radiculopathy since 4 years - on and off. On physical examination, there was no significant findings.

MRI study of lumbosacral spine revealed: Thickened filum terminale with a well-defined fusiform shaped lesion measuring approximately 3.5 cm in length and 0.5 cm in width displaying hyperintense signal on Sagittal T1W and T2W sequences and showing complete attenuation of signal on fat saturated STIR coronal sequence involving the posterior

central spinal canal along upper border of L3 to mid-level of L4 vertebral body.

The lesion is effacing and indenting the cauda equina. The lumbar canal and conus medularis appear normal. However conus is slightly low, terminating at L2.

Features are consistent with closed spinal dysraphism with filum terminale lipoma.(Figure 5) Mild disc bulge noted at L4/L5 and L5/S1 intervertebral disc levels.

Figure 6: a) T1 Sag and b) T2 Sag – Conus terminating at L2, with fusiform shaped hyperintense lesion in the thickened filum terminale (dashed yellow bracket) showing fat suppression in d) STIR Cor image.

Case 6:

A 31 year old pregnant woman came for MRI study of LS spine in view of tuft of hair in the lower back region as pre-requisite to the Spinal anesthesia for the LSCS surgery. Patient had no complaints. MRI study of Lumbosacral spine revealed: Nonunion of spinous process of L5 vertebra (bifid spine) however the skin and paraspinal muscles appear intact. A

linear T2 hypointense tract measuring ~ 3.7 mm in length and about 2 mm in width is seen extending from surface of the skin upto the posterior aspect of the thecal sac through the gap in the bifid spine at the level of L5. Conus medularis terminates at L3 vertebral body level.

Features are consistent with closed spinal dysraphism with dorsal dermal sinus tract. (Figure 6)

Figure 7: f) Hypertrichosis with dimple. a) T1 Sag – low lying conus at L3. b) T2 Sag - linear T2 hypointense tract (red →) seen extending from surface of the skin (red *) upto the posterior aspect of the thecal sac [c] through the gap in the bifid spine [as shown in d) T2 Cor and e) T2 Axial]at the level of L5.
Case 7:

A 11 year old female came to hospital for evaluation of short stature. Patient was referred to department of Radio-diagnosis to rule out neural tube defect / Spina bifida occulta.

MRI study of Thoraco lumbar Spine revealed: Altered thoraco-lumbar curvature. Vertebral segmentation anomaly in lower dorsal and lumbar vertebrae. A hemi / butterfly vertebrae is seen at D11 level with hypoplastic right posterior arch elements. Another hemi-vertebra is seen at L1 level on right side with fusion of its posterior arch elements with D12 vertebra. Another hemi-vertebra with partial block vertebra is seen at L2/ L3 level with fusion of their posterior arch elements. Conus is seen ending

at L4 level with tethering of the cauda nerve root – suggestive of low lying tethered cord. Defect seen in the posterior arch elements from L2/L3 to L4 level for a length of ~ 3.4 cm. There is slight posterior kinking of the cord at this level with tethering of nerve roots posteriorly, however no obvious herniation of meninges and CSF seen (no myelomeningocele). The defect is covered by subcutaneous tissue and skin – suggestive of spina bifida occulta. Focal area of intracord CSF intensity seen in lower cord at L1 to L2/L3 level - syrinx. Features suggestive of Vertebral segmentation anomaly of the lower dorsal and lumbar vertebrae as detailed.

Figure 8: a) & b) T2 Sag, c) T2 Cor – shows Hemi / butterfly vertebrae in multiple levels of dorso-lumbar spine (yellow →). d) low lying tethered spinal cord (*) at L4 level with dural ectasia. e) T2 Sag showing focal syrinx (red →). f) Abnormal angulation of coccyx.

Discussion:

Neural tube defects are the second most common major fetal congenital anomaly, second only to cardiac malformations, and occur as a result of inappropriate closure of the neural tube [8]. Spinal dysraphism refers to a spectrum of congenital malformations due to defective fusion of neural tube during embryological development of spine and spinal cord [9].

The etymologic origin of the term dysraphism is from the Greek words dys (bad) and raphé (suture); therefore, it should be applied only to primary neurulation abnormalities.

However, in medical practice, it is used to describe a diverse group of abnormalities of spinal cord development that occur between the 2nd and 6th

gestational weeks and show incomplete midline closure of mesenchymal, osseous, and nervous tissue [10]. SDs are a subtype of neural tube defects, with an estimated prevalence of about one to three per 1000 live births.

The lumbosacral spine is the most common site, involved in 90% of cases, followed by the thoracic spine (6%–8%) and cervical spine (2%–4%) [11,12].

Embryology

Development of spinal cord occurs during early embryogenesis (between 2-6 wk of gestation) in three main stages - gastrulation, primary neurulation and secondary neurulation [5].

Gastrulation is the process of addition of mesoderm between the epiblast and hypoblast of the bilaminar embryonic disc leading to the formation of the trilaminar embryonic disc during the second and third gestational weeks. .

The notochord is also formed at this stage [13]. The second stage in spinal development is primary neurulation (weeks 3–4) in which the notochord and overlying ectoderm interact to form the neural plate.

The neural plate bends and folds to form the neural tube, which then closes bidirectionally in a zipperlike manner [9]. Secondary neurulation occurs during the 5th and 6th week of gestation. Caudal to the primary neural tube, the tail bud is formed by a solid mass of totipotent cells. The secondary neural tube is formed by internal cavitation in the tail bud. This secondary neural tube joins the primary neural

tube creating a continuous structure. By retrogressive differentiation, the tail bud regresses and forms the filum terminale (FT) and the tip of the conus medullaris [14].

Deviation in any of these steps can lead to SD.

Classification

The most commonly recognized classification of spinal dysraphism is that proposed by Tortori-Donati, which subdivides spinal dysraphic entities on the basis of their clinical neuroradiologic characteristics into two main categories, open and closed, and further subdivides the closed spinal dysraphisms into those with and without subcutaneous masses [8] (figure).

Figure 9:

Open Spinal Dysraphism

In this category, the spinal defect is not covered by skin, and there is direct communication between the herniating sac and the external environment. Open neural tube defects are considered a neonatal emergency because of the risk of infection and are treated immediately after birth, without preoperative imaging. There are four distinct entities in this

category: myelomeningocele, myelocele, hemimyocele, and hemimyoelomeningocele.

Myelomeningocele and myelocele:

Myelomeningoceles and myeloceles are caused by defective closure of the primary neural tube and are characterized clinically by exposure of the neural placode through a midline skin defect on the back.

Myelomeningoceles account for more than 98% of open spinal dysraphisms [15]. Myeloceles are rare. Open spinal dysraphisms are often diagnosed clinically, so imaging is not always performed. When imaging is performed, the main differentiating feature between a myelomeningocele and myelocele is the position of the neural placode relative to the skin surface [16]. The neural placode protrudes above the skin surface with a myelomeningocele and is flush with the skin surface with a myelocele.

Hemimyelomeningocele or hemimyelocele:

Hemimyelo-meningocele is an extremely rare condition resulting from defective gastrulation with failed midline notochordal integration and an additional fault in the primary neurulation of one hemicord. In hemimyelo-meningo-coele, there is a widening of the subarachnoid space posteriorly raising the hemiplacode above the skin surface, whereas in hemimyelocele, the hemiplacode is flush with the skin surface [1,17,18].

Closed Spinal Dysraphism with a Subcutaneous Mass

The main entities in this subcategory include lipomyelomeningoceles, lipomyeloceles, meningoceles, and terminal myelocystoceles. Both lipomyeloceles and lipomyelomeningoceles are characterized by a combination of a lipoma, neural tissue, and CSF, extending through the defective posterior vertebral elements and blending with the posterior subcutaneous tissues. The neural placode–lipoma interface allows these entities to be differentiated from others.

In lipomyeloceles, the neural placode rests in the confines of the spinal canal, while in lipomyelomeningoceles, it bulges through the dysraphic defect into the dorsal subcutaneous tissues [19]. A meningocele is a closed neural tube defect with the dura mater, the arachnoid mater, and CSF herniating into the subcutaneous tissue. In addition, nerve roots and/or hypertrophied portions of the filum terminale can herniate through this defect. The spinal cord does not herniate through the defect, which allows meningoceles to be differentiated from lipomyelomeningoceles [6].

Myelocystocele, a rare subtype of closed spinal dysraphism, refers to a widely dilated syrinx in the neural placode, extending through a vertebral osseous defect into the subcutaneous tissues, and is invariably surrounded by a meningocele, resulting in a clinically and radiologically observed mass. These can be terminal, in which the terminal ventricle in the caudal end of the spinal cord is dilated (syringocele) or nonterminal and observed in the cervical, thoracic, or lumbar region [20].

Closed spinal dysraphisms without a subcutaneous mass

Simple dysraphic states

Intradural lipoma: Adipose cells inside the dural sac constitute this benign lesion [21]. The embryologic mechanism is similar to that of the lipomyelocele. A subpial lipomatous lesion is seen on MRI lying between the fibres of the placode [1].

Lipoma of the filum terminale: Improper cavitation of the tail bud with continued presence of cells that can mature into adipocytes after separation of the neuroectoderm from the cutaneous ectoderm leads to a filum terminale (FT) lipoma [6]. Filar lipoma is seen on MRI as a small T1 and T2 hyperintense lesion in the region of FT without any communication with the medullary cone [1].

Persistence of the terminal ventricle (fifth ventricle): This is a small ependymal-lined cavity centrally located within the conus medullaris [22]. The fifth ventricle is formed during secondary neurulation because of partial regression of the terminal ventricle. It remains continuous with the central canal of the spinal cord [6]. It follows CSF signal intensity on all MRI sequences without any post-contrast enhancement [1].

Complex dysraphic states:

Complex dysraphic states can be divided into two categories: disorders of midline notochordal integration, which include dorsal enteric fistula, neurenteric cyst, and diastematomyelia, and disorders of notochordal formation, which include caudal agenesis and segmental spinal dysgenesis.

A) Disorders of midline notochordal integration:

Dorsal enteric fistula and neurenteric cyst—A dorsal enteric fistula occurs when there is an abnormal connection between the skin surface and bowel. Neurenteric cysts represent a more localized form of dorsal enteric fistula. These cysts are lined with mucin-secreting epithelium similar to the gastrointestinal tract and are typically located in the cervicothoracic spine anterior to the spinal cord [23].

Diastematomyelia—Separation of the spinal cord into two hemicords is referred to as diastematomyelia. The two hemicords are usually symmetric, although the length of separation is variable. There are two types of diastematomyelia.

In type 1, the two hemicords are located within individual dural tubes separated by an osseous or cartilaginous septum. In type 2, there is a single dural tube containing two hemicords, sometimes with an intervening fibrous septum [24]. Diastematomyelia can present clinically with scoliosis and tethered-cord syndrome. A hairy tuft on the patient's back can be a distinctive finding on physical examination [25].

B) Disorders of notochordal formation:

Caudal agenesis: Caudal agenesis refers to total or partial agenesis of the spinal column and may be associated with the following: anal imperforation, genital anomalies, renal dysplasia or aplasia, pulmonary hypoplasia, or limb abnormalities. Caudal agenesis can be categorized into two types. In type 1, there is a high position and abrupt termination of the conus medullaris. In type 2, there is a low position and tethering of the conus medullaris [26].

Segmental spinal dysgenesis: The clinical–radiologic definition of segmental spinal dysgenesis includes several entities: segmental agenesis or dysgenesis of the thoracic or lumbar spine, segmental abnormality of the spinal cord or nerve roots, congenital paraparesis or paraplegia, and congenital lower limb deformities. Three-dimensional CT reconstructions can be helpful in showing various vertebral segmentation anomalies (27).

Conclusion:

Congenital malformations of the spinal cord represent a heterogeneous group of abnormalities that usually occur owing to derangements in the steps of the complex cascade of spinal embryology. As discussed earlier, they are divided into two main groups: open SDs, which represent a medical emergency owing to direct environmental exposure of neural tissue, and closed SDs, in which the anomalies show skin coverage. SDs represent an important cause of childhood morbidity owing to not only neurologic impairment but also associated malformations, as in the respiratory and gastrointestinal tracts, leading to profound economic and psychosocial impact. Neuroimaging plays a pivotal role in diagnosis and presurgical evaluation of SDs. Therefore, knowledge of spinal cord embryology and the main imaging findings of these malformations is essential for the radiologist. Therefore, a rational approach based on the correlation of clinical, embryological and neuroimaging information considerably aids the diagnosis in the vast majority of cases.

MRI is the imaging modality of choice for evaluation of the soft tissue anomalies of Spinal dysraphism especially spinal cord anomalies. Multiplanar reformatted CT is an excellent imaging modality for characterization of vertebral segmentation defects, spinal curvature anomalies associated with spinal dysraphism. Thus CT and MRI together play an important role in the complete radiological evaluation of spinal dysraphism.

MRI is study of choice when surgical therapy is required it provides anatomic details of spinal cord, intervertebral disc space, CSF with in the subarachnoid space.

Authors' contributions:

Dr Hemavathi Ayyappan - conceptualization, data curation, investigation, methodology, project administration, visualization, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing; **Dr Puneet Shirbur** -conceptualization, methodology, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing; **Dr Valambige mudalagirigowda puttaraju** - conceptualization, visualization, supervision, writing—original draft. All authors approved the final manuscript as submitted and agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Data Availability:

All datasets generated or analyzed during this study are included in the manuscript.

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